

Education and Development: Way Forward in Repositioning Education in the 4th Industrial Revolution

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Abstract: Teacher education is a vital part of the educational process. In the last decade, teachers have made significant progress in the field of teacher education. In this paper, we discuss the current state of the art in the teaching of English as a foreign language. We also review the current research trends in the subject of teaching and learning, examining teachers' educational needs and emerging priorities, and examining their perspectives on teacher education and development. Now, it becomes necessary that the teachers should change or modify themselves to the demands or the needs that are arising in society. That change; change in the teacher's training; teaching and learning materials; theoretical and practical aspects; curriculum; professional development; evaluation and assessment and many more, etc., in the same area, has also to be taken into consideration. This paper focuses on the study of the concept of teacher education, its various components, and various facets of teacher development and associated factors. Teacher Education and Development should be prioritized, we can empower teachers to provide high-quality education and prepare students for success in our society.

Keywords: Teacher education, teacher development, ICT-based teaching, curriculum development, evaluation, assessment.

Introduction

The Fourth Industrial Revolution has accelerated technical advancement in the twenty-first century. Thus, recent years have been characterized by a rapid acceptance of technology and the development of new interests and tools in all areas of the educational sphere. Several studies in the literature have acknowledged the use of various educational technologies for instructional objectives. In particular, the use of wireless technology, web-based and mobile technologies, digital platforms, computer projection systems, active gaming devices, Moodle, and software create new options for teachers and students (Adelore & Itasanmi, 2016; Semiz & Ince, 2012).

The integration of ICT into education necessitates frequent and adequate ICT training for teachers as part of their professional development (Dlamini & Mbatha, 2018; Chisango et al, 2020). According to Chisango and Lesame (2019), teachers should receive regular updates on their expertise, knowledge, and specific ICT skills in order to promote efficient ICT integration into teaching and learning and improve adoption through continuous and frequent training. Furthermore, Ojo and Adu (2018), Madoda and Chigona (2019) argue for the availability of ICT resources to all schools, as well as frequent and essential professional development for teachers to ensure effective use of ICT resources in teaching and learning.

Teacher Education and Development refers to the process of equipping teachers with the necessary knowledge, skills, and values to effectively teach and support student learning. Teacher Education and Development aims to

foster a culture of continuous learning, collaboration, and excellence in teaching, ultimately impacting student achievement and success. While some teachers utilize the internet to capture students' interest, they are unsure how to use it to help the teaching and learning process. In light of this, pre-service teacher technology training has become an important component of teacher training programs to ensure that aspiring teachers are adequately equipped to use technology in their classrooms (Gulbahar, 2008; Batane & Ngwako, 2017).

Teacher education programmes are related to developing the proficiency and competence of the teachers that can motivate and empower the teacher to meet their requirements of their profession and help them to face the challenges. As per National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) teacher education is “A program of education, research, and training of persons to teach from pre-primary to higher education level.” Kumar (2019) describes, “Training is given to animals and circus performers, while education is to human beings. “Teacher education is concerned with both pre-service and in-service teacher education. In other words, teacher education refers to the process and procedures that are designed by the policymakers to equip all the prospective teachers with all the resources needed in this program like skills, knowledge, curriculum, teaching materials, equipment, etc. For this, there are components of teacher education that all the teachers must go through.

Components of Teacher Education

Three components must be considered as important elements for the teacher education who are to be taught about the skills and knowledge. After that, it will help them in their teaching and most importantly, it will help them professionally.

Components:

Teaching skills: It includes providing training and practice with different techniques, skills, approaches, opportunities, and strategies that will help the teachers to plan out and deliver their instructions in the classroom which will provide them with appropriate reinforcement so that there can be an effective evaluation. It includes effective classroom management skills, preparation and use of instructional materials communication skills.

Pedagogical theory: It includes foundations of knowledge like philosophical, sociological and psychological subjects that will give them the basic knowledge to do practice of teaching skills in the artificial classroom. It is based on the stage-specific theory i.e., needs and requirements of the students.

Professional skills: After learning the basic knowledge about the skills, techniques and strategies in an effective manner, professional skills will help the teacher to uplift themselves in this industry and so, their professional growth will also increase. In this industry, teachers will learn and understand about the soft skills like counseling, interpersonal communication, computer interface, management skills and lifelong learning skills and all these will help the student teachers to bring a change in themselves in terms of knowledge, attitude, behavior, personality etc.

As soon as all these things are taken into consideration then, they start developing themselves.

Teacher Development and the 4th Industrial Revolution

It refers to the continuous process to develop, change, and grow themselves in terms of professionalism throughout their career. In this sense, the teacher needs to learn each and everything that is coming in the way of the development of the process, so that all those can be used by them in a real situation, and with that; their personal and professional growth will be possible side by side. The best way to grow is to take up their teaching done in the classroom and try to improve upon it or take feedback either from the students or from colleagues regarding the teaching done in the classrooms.

James (2001) mentions, “Teachers can best learn through their own experience, following the guidelines from the course book, experimenting with the new curriculum, taking a new role, changing the course books and trying out different ideas in classroom practice”. He also says that collaboration in teaching like team teaching, joint work, peer observation, supervision, support, and discussion plays an important role in teacher development. But it will be possible only when no one is forcing them to develop i.e., the teachers should motivate themselves that they have to change themselves and need to adapt to the changes and innovations coming in the teaching-learning process.

Teacher needs to update themselves as a part of their development to adjust themselves in the new kinds of issues and challenges coming by and new ideas and concepts coming up in the disciplines and to act accordingly with the changing needs and desires of the learners with time and economic, social and technological change (Gnawali, 2012). Gnawali also reported that without teacher development, the profession will be monotonous, tedious, slow and uninspiring. So, development starts from that day only when they take admission in Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) course where the foundation of education, skills and basic knowledge are given to all pupil- teachers and they move on, changes come in them and at last, they have to teach the students in the institutions but again for that need to adapt the changes coming in these areas.

Important Factors for Teacher Development in the 4th Industrial Revolution

Some factors help the teachers to develop themselves more so, research takes place which is conducted in every area but when we talk about the development of the teacher then all the things which are related to them whether it is for the pre-service or in-service program. The researcher takes the concerned area where they feel any kind of innovation or the need for modification is required. Thus, the following are the emergent research inclinations in the field of Teacher Education.

Figure 1: Leaning Areas in Research in Teacher Education

In today’s era of development, society wishes that students should have an overall development in every area. School changes their pattern of teaching-learning methods accordingly. With this, students construct their

knowledge and skills; do experiments with which they further gain experience, etc. James (2010) led study on communication in second language (English) for teaching and learning. Teacher is undertaking a difficult step of imparting language skills to the students as they are not in position of learning new basic skills of language at school and at college level. Students require high level of skills in critical analysis and literary appreciation but they are failing in this which lead to decline in the socio-cultural development. Instructional communication is the best method to impart a second language. Bhati (2016) studied the effectiveness of cooperative learning methods for teaching English students at secondary schools. The researcher wants to compare different teaching methods.

Teachers must change the roles of knowledge transference to help, promote, and encourage learners to acquire knowledge from various media and learning centers. Josephine (2016) studied the effectiveness of a blended learning programme on academic achievement in teaching physical science among student teachers of Pondicherry, where blended learning was found to be an appropriate method to use in the classroom for increasing academic achievement. Here, students are given the freedom to understand the concept on their level. After going through the above research, it was found that teachers should use those methods which suit best to them best for lifelong learning.

ICT Based Teaching

In the world of globalization, every person wants to connect globally which improves their knowledge, skills, information, and utilizing new technology and implementing all those in their real life such that development would occur. ICT used in school, colleges and universities helps the students and teachers to make their content delivery effective which enables them to understand the concept easily. Students and teachers can make the use of recent technology for upgrading themselves. Kumari (2013) emphasized her focus on the study of attitude towards ICT of science teachers at the secondary level in Shillong. Due to lack of using ICT, teachers are lacking behind in leadership, resulting in a decrease in teaching efficiency. Kumari (2013) carried the study of teacher effectiveness of ICT familiar and ICT unfamiliar college teachers. The knowledge of ICTs is essential for college teachers as it increases teacher's performance and also students' achievement (Dwivedi, 2016).

Sridharan (2016) researched the attitude and aptitude of teacher instructors towards ICT. However, due to advancements in technology, a digital gap has been found between the teachers who have access to and control over technology and those who have no access. Realizing the importance of information technology, ICT is now used by teachers to deal with content in a classroom creating an appropriate environment for the media to be used effectively with free access to many information resources but for that teachers should know about these. Then only, he will be able to implement it in the classroom as a teaching material for that he/she should be self-confident. If we want pupil teachers to use technology then, it is the need that arises to prepare them and motivate them during pre-service training-based teaching.

Some examples of ICT-based teaching include: Online learning platforms and Learning Management Systems (LMS), Digital recourses and multimedia content (e.g., videos, podcasts, interactive simulations), Virtual classrooms and video conferencing, Mobile learning and apps, Gamification and game-based learning, Virtual and augmented reality experiences, Online collaboration and communication tools (e.g., discussion forums, email, instant messaging), Digital assessment and feedback tools. From the above research, ICT is the best method to increase teaching performance, and attitude which ultimately increases students' achievement.

Curriculum Development

It is an important tool for making the interaction between teachers and students where teachers change the curriculum according to the needs, and requirements arising from students and society. Demands for all these will be completed when proper supply will be available within the institution and with teachers. After that, teachers will develop their curriculum accordingly with the limited resources available. Lodh (2011) in his study of the science curriculum of secondary schools in the state of Tripura found that the curriculum needs to be changed according to present needs so that overall development can be done by acquiring scientific knowledge, skills and experiences. For qualitative improvement in teacher education, there is a need for re-defining the teacher's role within the framework of pre-service and in-service learning. For that programme, collaboration and networking are essential for ensuring the effective and efficient implementation of the teacher education programme (Taneja, 2014).

The main aim of evaluation is to better the course for students of the future. De Kalidas (2018) studied the relevance of the teachers training curriculum in present scenario. His was a historical approach showing the absence of humanistic and nationalistic qualities in the curriculum and also views the present

The scenario of the society. He recommends a change and modifications of the teacher's training curriculum i.e., B.Ed. with immediate effect to save Indian society and to flourish India by making out the best with traditional values, humanitarian outlook, nation-loving principles, and proper actualization of constitutional values. It can be solved by modification with all human values and man-making education and the interest of the nation with top-most priority and urgency. It concluded through research review that changes in curriculum build effective steps towards development among teachers and students.

Evaluation and Assessment Process

Both the words are used as a synonym at various places but there is a difference between them. Evaluation is to make the person ranked/positioned in a classroom whereas assessment is made to identify the performance level of students. It plays important roles in the life of teachers, students and parents, where students are continuously evaluated through formative and summative way. Accordingly, suggestions are given to them for improvement and teachers keep in mind through which methods they will teach next time for better improvement. It also plays an important role in teacher perspectives where teacher programme curriculum changes with the rise in demand and supplies them in the proper form, making them effective and competent teachers.

Kaur (2013) evaluated quality assurance in higher education. The researcher focuses on catering to the needs arising in the market for providing an effective quality of education at a higher level. Here, the student is evaluating the teaching methodology and curriculum for making it out whether it is focusing on the quality of implementing it to the students and changes as per the rise in needs. Panda (2019) focused on an evaluative study of the effectiveness of in-service education programme of elementary teachers. The researcher proposes to study the development of in-service education to assess effectiveness, to study the education needs of the teachers and to find out the priorities arising in the area of in-service education, to study the views of teachers on utility and to suggest guidelines for effective organization of in-service education programme. The development of innovative strategies should be encouraged to ensure the effectiveness of the in-service training programme. It can be concluded that most of the papers were related to evaluation not assessment. Researchers conducted in the area of evaluation have focused on the area of higher level and university level, and not on the area of primary and secondary level.

Teacher Development

The teacher tries to develop themselves in every area they get the opportunity to develop in terms of knowledge, skills, ICT, research area and many more etc. so that all these things can be imparted or been inculcated among the students for development. Teachers will develop only when they want to change or modify themselves rather than someone pushing them to upgrade themselves. Tunio (2012) studied the effectiveness of teacher training programmes in English for secondary and higher secondary schools, forcing on all trained English teachers at Larkana district. The researcher conducted the study on the basis of government educational policies to provide qualitative education to the students through effective instructional methodologies. At last, an objective was achieved where teachers themselves get academic benefits.

Teaching will only be effective when the teacher gives quality of education through the improvement in teacher performance as Thakur (2017) inferred from the research on teacher effectiveness as related to cognitive style and emotional competence. After identifying the intervening variables, improvement can be done by knowing about cognitive styles and emotional competence. Ullah *et al.* (2019) studied the effectiveness of teacher education programmes in developing selected teaching skills for secondary level and means to improve the programmes for pre-service teacher education programmes in Punjab. The researcher mainly focused on the development of skills and behavior of the graduates that can better be evaluated while they were performing the skills and exhibiting the behavior in the classroom. Therefore, the continuous classroom observation method was considered the most appropriate for this study. It was observed through above research that teachers should develop or change themselves in the area of primary and elementary level.

Challenges of Education in the 4th Industrial Revolution

While the fourth industrial revolution offers numerous advantages, it also presents several significant obstacles. At the same time, the revolution may result in increased inequality, particularly due to its ability to destabilize labor markets. The fourth industrial revolution presents a number of challenges that must be overcome, ranging from income inequality to cybersecurity. Technological and scientific developments fuel global transformation. They cause rippling impacts in society, institutions, and economies. They will change the way we live, work, and interact with one another.

Understanding these emerging technologies and their disruptive potential is crucial for all governments, particularly developing ones. The fourth industrial revolution may have a wide range of effects on society and the economy. (Prisecaru 2016). First, a high proportion of individuals worldwide are anticipated to utilize social media platforms to connect, learn, and share knowledge. Second, a wide range of inventive producers and rivals will have simple access to digital marketing, sales, and distribution platforms, resulting in improved product and

service quality and pricing. Third, customers will become increasingly involved in the production and distribution processes. The key implications of this revolution on the business environment are the changes in consumer expectations, product quality, the shift toward collaborative innovation and innovations in educational forms.

“We stand on the brink of a technological revolution that will fundamentally alter the way we live, work, and relate to one another. In its scale, scope, and complexity, the transformation will be unlike anything humankind has experienced before. We do not yet know just how it will unfold, but one thing is clear: the response to it must be integrated and comprehensive, involving all stakeholders of the global polity, from the public and private sectors to academic and civil society.” (Schwab 2015).

In addition to the threat of massive job displacement under the ongoing fourth industrial revolution, there are a variety of challenges, such as cybersecurity, hacking, risk assessment, and others. (Lambert 2017) A higher level of alert is raised up when our lives become extensively connected to various devices, from our cell phones, cars, and light switches to our home security cameras, and smart speakers. One of the biggest trends in 2018 Consumer Electronics Show is that everything is connected and there is no going back. (Goode 2018).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Teacher education programmes in the 4th Industrial Revolution include pre-service and in- service teacher training programmes. In pre-service programmes, pupil-teachers are given knowledge in pedagogy, foundation of education and practical knowledge. In in-service programmes teachers try to upgrade themselves in every area they get the opportunity to develop themselves which would ultimately increase the teaching process during classroom transactions when appropriate methods will be used by the teacher. These will be helpful for the students and pupil-teachers to upgrade themselves. After the emergent inclinations discussed above, the need is mentioned so that it might help the upcoming researchers to do research in that area for more development.

From the findings of the study, the researcher, therefore, recommends the following: Pre-service teacher training programmes should include:

Knowledge in pedagogy

Foundations of education

Practical knowledge

In addition, in-service teacher training programmes should provide opportunities for teachers to:

Upgrade their knowledge and skills

Develop themselves in various areas

Use appropriate methods in classroom transactions to improve the teaching process.

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